

EVALUATING THE EFFECT OF ACUTE RADIATION ON ORGANISM BIOTOPES

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ABSTRACT

It was recognized that all of these aspects depend on the radiation dose and the level of development of compensatory-adaptive mechanisms in the animal organism.

External influences that negatively affect the body include acute and chronic radiation, the level of microbiological changes caused by them, changes in the normal microflora of the large intestine of experimental animals, and the ability of representatives of this biotope to translocate from the gastrointestinal tract to the internal organs of the body were shown. In order to identify and evaluate microbiological aspects such as the impact of different levels of radiation on the standard microflora in the biotopes of the organism and the ability of microorganisms to translocate, it was recommended to improve the evaluation methodology for the selected total acute and chronic radiation models and to implement them in a unified manner.

The purpose. The response of laboratory animals involved in the study to external stimuli was observed.

Materials and methods. Given the high probability of acute and chronic radiation exposure mainly in adults, laboratory animals were taken at the age of puberty (3 months), healthy, weighing at least 160-180 g, and rats of this weight were selected for the study. Only male rats were used in the experiments, as the various hormonal and other changes in the female rat's body due to puberty do not ensure the purity of the experiment and the validity of the results obtained.

Results. The reaction of laboratory animals involved in the study to external influences was visually observed. γ -irradiation, which has a high probability of negative effects on the human body in acute radiation, was selected, which was given once at a dose of 5 Gray, and total irradiation was performed to have an equal effect on the body, and the dose was chosen so that it would definitely have a negative effect, but would not lead to an immediate lethal state (5 Gy). Since the laboratory animals were divided into 2 groups (group 1 - those who received the "Lactonzopolis-AWL" biologically active supplement (BAS) for 30 days; group 2 - those who did not receive "Lactonzopolis-AWL" BAS), the results were presented by group. On the 1st day after acute radiation, various changes in laboratory animals were observed in

all of them, and on the 4th day, a difference was observed in the numbers obtained between the groups. The results obtained show that the total, single-time acute radiation exposure changed not only the body's organs and systems, but also its response to external influences.

In the prepared experimental models, the following distinctive differences were identified in the state and behavioral response of laboratory animals under the influence of acute and chronic radiation: firstly, the state and behavioral response of laboratory animals under acute radiation was observed in all animals (100.0%), while in chronic radiation, this indicator varied from 3.33% to 75.0%; secondly, while all signs of behavioral response changed uniformly in acute radiation, these changes did not manifest themselves uniformly in chronic radiation; thirdly, in white-bred rats, unlike acute radiation, no respiratory acceleration was observed in chronic radiation.

Conclusion. It was recognized that all of these aspects depend on the radiation dose and the level of development of compensatory-adaptive mechanisms in the animal organism

